

Technology use in Government School Libraries in Medellin, Colombia

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School libraries have been widely studied in Colombia from infrastructure capacities to their importance in educational institutions. However, these studies have failed to illustrate librarians' perceptions of technologies, their adoption and how students use technologies within their schools. This research presents a new approach to school libraries in Colombia by identifying technology adoption, use and use of open source materials within public school libraries using a mixed-methods approach. Results reveal low technology adoption among school librarians and high use for students in social media and mobile devices.

Introduction

Many public school libraries around the world have seen their budgets reduced over time. This is true for Medellín, Colombia, where government schools face challenges from insufficient resources, unqualified staff and spaces used as storage, to lack of preparedness, visibility, and, in some cases, lack of libraries within the institutions. In this context, many school librarians are employed for purposes different from library and pedagogical goals and students cannot obtain the benefits from a school librarian devoted entirely to them.

On the other hand, technologies have been playing a significant role within libraries from automation software to programs designed to help librarians interact and promote reading-writing skills effectively with their students. Therefore, school librarians must seek new paths in order, not only to meet their users' needs and leverage low-cost technologies to offer modern services, but to stay relevant within their schools. However, aforementioned circumstances entangled in government school libraries in Columbia hamper the quality of education and school librarians' reputation who struggle to keep libraries open and staffed. This situation has also negatively impacted government school librarians' image among highly-educated library science professionals who opt to work in other types of libraries.

Review of Literature

School libraries in developing countries face critical budget constraints (Santos-Diaz, 2017; Serna, 2017, McEwan, 2015), which prevent them from taking advantage of technology tools to meet their users' needs. Tools such as social media networks can be used to connect with students and parents, post messages about future events, offer extended hours and meetings, and host book clubs (Kirkland, 2007; Lawrence, 2014, Hanson-Baldauf, 2009; Silverman, 2013; Ulusoy & Atar, 2016). Collaborative tools in the cloud are available to work and share collaboratively (Scheeren, 2012;